

LIVING WITH CANCER: AN INSIDE LOOK AT THE FAMILIES AND CAREGIVERS OF
PATIENTS WHO HAVE BEEN DIAGNOSED WITH CANCER

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For many years, researchers have studied the effects of cancer, both in the physical and psychological aspects. In more recent years, there have been discussions about the people who are also affected by a cancer diagnosis, including family and friends of the patient. A caregiver is responsible for ensuring that the best treatment is given to the patient, keeping up with medications, and making the patient feel supported. To properly care for the individual, the caregiver will need to make changes to their daily routine. These changes can influence the psychological and physical aspects of an individual.

In this research project, I investigated individuals who have taken the responsibility of being a caregiver to someone who has been diagnosed with cancer. Many caregivers are family members or friends of the patients. Oftentimes, they are not paid for this role. The research presented suggests that a cancer diagnosis changes the family dynamics and is an incredibly overwhelming process for everyone involved. The caregivers of the patient tend to experience a psychological and even a physical shift in their everyday lives. The research also emphasizes the importance of having a good support system while dealing with this illness. Many factors can stress out the caregivers regarding the cancer patient such as the care they are receiving, the duration of the treatment, and not being able to understand what is happening. The purpose of this research is to examine the impact that a cancer diagnosis has on caregivers.

The role of the family is vital to an individual who is currently undergoing treatment for a certain disease, especially a disease as intense as cancer. It is important that the patients feel loved and cared for by the people closest to them. However, as family members fill the role of caregivers or become more involved in the patient's life, they tend to experience various emotions such as sadness, anger, and grief. Aside from the feelings that are associated with a

cancer diagnosis, many disparities within the medical field can alter the treatment or perceptions of the diagnosis.

Literature Review

There are studies regarding the differences in cancers. Lee, Navajas, and Liu conducted a study that examined ovarian cancer in Asian American women. Ovarian cancer is the most fatal cancer of the female reproductive system; however, its etiology is often misunderstood. The researchers, before beginning their study, found that across the major races in the United States, ovarian cancer incidence is low among Asian American women (Lee, Navajas & Liu, 2019). The problem was that previous observations aggregated Asian Americans as a single group. The researchers of this study found that it is important to separate the ethnic Asian population as it will help produce useful information and help others better understand ovarian cancer. The purpose of this study is to further investigate the rates of ovarian cancer in Asian American groups as separate groups versus one whole group, which is what previous cancer research in the United States has been doing. The purpose of focusing on each group separately is to determine if there have been any ethnic-specific differences that may have been overlooked in previous studies and how that affects the caregiving and treatment process.

This study hypothesized that the rate of incidence may vary when each Asian American ethnicity is considered separately. The groups examined in this study include Chinese, Filipino, Asian Indian/Pakistani, Korean, Japanese, and Vietnamese. The research methodology included 13 population-based cancer registries which represent 54% of the U.S. Asian and Pacific Islander populations. The research also included ovarian cancer cases diagnosed between 1990 and 2014 and these cases were identified using the International Classification of Diseases for Oncology.

Only malignant cases with a known age at diagnosis and race/ethnicity were included in the study (Lee, Navajas & Liu, 2019). The main findings of the study showed that Asian American ethnic groups had a lower occurrence of ovarian cancer compared to non-Hispanic whites. Asian Indian/Pakistani women were identified as having the highest incidence of ovarian cancer. This study was beneficial in gaining more information about Asian American women and their correlation to ovarian cancer. However, there is a lack of supporting evidence for cancer data as well as population data regarding Asian American ethnicities. A limitation of the study would be that this study only focuses on the Asian American population in a few cities which could lead to misclassification. There were a few strengths of the study such as the way the researchers were able to separate the groups and examine them separately. This study is important in examining cancer and the way it affects family members because it supports the emotions of anger since many feel as if they are being overlooked in science.

A study was conducted to explore the challenges faced by Iranian family caregivers of cancer patients (Nemati, Rassouli, et, al., 2018). The researchers of this study saw those caregivers of cancer patients endure a lot of emotions and changes in their life. The researchers of this study wanted to better understand the trials and tribulations caregivers go through to ensure they provide the best support and treatment to their patients. Essentially, this curiosity prompted this research to be conducted. The purpose of this research is to address the needs and concerns of the patient's caregivers. This study is important when examining cancer because it allows the audience to get a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the various issues faced by family caregivers. There is a growing increase in cancer diagnosis, and there are also

many changes being made to treatment protocols which can result in expensive health care. Due to the numerous changes to protocols, there is an increase in demand for informal caregivers.

According to this study, informal caregivers can be defined as family or friends of the patients (Nemati, Rassouli, et, al., 2018). The research focuses on unfamiliar tasks that these caregivers are expected to fulfill such as the need to administer medicine and so on. This study is significant because it also emphasizes the need for caregivers to receive support as well. It also demonstrates the importance of having good medical staff to ensure that everyone is aware of what is going on through honesty. It is important to have good doctors because that will help eliminate some stress and tension that resides within caregivers. The study was conducted through a qualitative study where semi-structured interviews were held with 21 family caregivers of cancer patients which were selected through purposive sampling. The study also consisted of people who are at least 20 years old, live with the cancer patient and are the caregiver for at least eight hours a day, have no history of mental disease, and can speak Persian. One weakness of this study would be that this research only focuses on Iranian culture which leaves questions about other cultures and other places in the world. A strength of this study would be that the researchers were able to categorize the feelings reported by caregivers. Those categories are broken down into themes: setback, confusion, and uncertainty.

Many changes occur once a cancer diagnosis is present, family dynamics are not the same and they either change for better or for worse. In this article by Nikolaos Vrontaras, he examines how a family changes after they have received a cancer diagnosis. This is an important aspect to study because it shows how overwhelming cancer is for everyone involved. It also emphasizes the need for support for caregivers because they experience a lot of emotions and

aren't quite sure how to properly cope with their situation. This study can be compared to the previous study mentioned (Nemati, Rassouli, et, al., 2018) because both analyze family members and how they feel throughout the treatment of the patient. Both studies look at both the positive and negative emotions associated with cancer.

This study conducted by Vrontaras focuses on the family members' feelings as well as how the patient views their family. Some of the positive changes reported from this study would be better communication and better relationships being formed. The negative changes include a disruption in traditional family activities and having to rethink plans such as marriage or vacations. These changes are important to note because they highlight the feelings of the family members and demonstrate the increased levels of distress they are experiencing. This study included eight individuals who have been diagnosed with cancer, seven women and one man. Also, the participants needed to be at least 18 years old, diagnosed with cancer, not have experienced any relapses, treatment had ended a year before this study, and the diagnosis must be recent (Vrontaras, 2018). One of the weaknesses of this study would be that the participants shared similar backgrounds which did not allow for much diversity. Also, the study was not able to tell much about gender differences because only one male participant was involved. This is like the past articles mentioned because it highlights the various emotions involved with such a diagnosis.

A cancer diagnosis is not an easy result to hear, and many people fear what could happen emotionally, physically, and mentally to themselves and everyone around them (Wozniak, Izycki, 2014). In previous articles mentioned, we can see the psychological and physical shifts that people experience while trying to cope with the diagnosis. We also can see how important it is to

have trust in the health care system, even though there may be some disparities, and how important it is for everyone involved to feel supported. This next article focuses on similar topics. This article focuses on the different ways a cancer diagnosis can change a family and the relationships they have with one another. This article specifically looks at the romantic relationships between partners. It was shown through this study that a cancer diagnosis affects romantic relationships because it causes issues with intimacy and can affect the relationship with children. Those couples who have children experience a lot of stress since the individual with cancer is not able to be as active with the children as they wish, couples who do not have kids but would like to begin a family have to reconsider. The main findings of this study identify various areas that affect family functioning such as cancer can be a potential threat to family plans and traditions.

Cancer also affects the work and academic aspects of life for caregivers. This article also identifies various phases that patients and their loved ones go through such as the recovery phase which calls for celebration and uncertainty, and the end-of-life phase which is typically the hardest phase to deal with (Wozniak, Izycki, 2014). A weakness of this study is that there is no cancer type identified meaning we are unsure whether the cancer is referred to as liver or breast cancer. This means that the study is generalizing all forms of cancer and grouping them into one universal experience, which is not the case for different types of cancer. This study is important in helping people understand the psychological changes faced by caregivers of cancer patients.

The previous studies have mentioned the emotions associated with a cancer diagnosis, the articles talk about the experiences of the patient and family members. This article has a similar perspective but focuses primarily on levels of depression and anxiety related to adult patients

who have recently been diagnosed with cancer and their adult relatives (Edwards & Clarke, 2004). This article also emphasizes the importance of having a good support system. This finding is like the previous articles because they also discuss why having a strong support system is needed, it helps to eliminate some emotions, (Nemati, Rassouli, et, al., 2018), (Vrontaras, 2018). This article also emphasizes the importance of having a strong, supportive caregiver. However, that can cause caregivers to hide their emotions which may make the process harder for them.

This article presented by Edwards and Clarke (2004), focuses on breast cancer, colorectal cancer, and prostate cancer. The focus on specific types of cancer is a strength of this article because it gives perspective on different types of cancer instead of generalizing. The research found that if the family is cooperative, then levels of depression and anxiety will be minimized. The author also argues that family members should be willing to talk about their emotions regarding treatment and that health professionals should guide everyone through the treatment process. The results showed that those with breast cancer had the highest levels of depression and anxiety. A weakness of this article would be that there was no evidence for advanced levels of cancer and didn't include the input of family members which would have helped to strengthen the overall findings. If the study examined advanced stages, we might expect to see different levels of depression and anxiety in individuals.

The relationships patients have with caregivers, family members, friends, and their partners can either be an advantage or a disadvantage. This article examines how caregivers react to the process of being responsible for the cancer patient. This article takes an in-depth look at the psychological distress that caregivers endure and looks at the increased levels of distress. The main findings were that many caregivers and partners have trouble processing the diagnosis but

refuse to seek help for themselves. It was also found that many caregivers develop psychiatric disorders and experience high levels of emotional distress. It was also found that women caregivers report higher levels of distress than male caregivers. Due to the increased distress, women tend to have a more negative perspective on the caregiving role. This article is important because it helps researchers understand the intensity of being a caregiver and how much this affects them psychologically.

Numerous studies examine the feelings and perceptions of the patient, however, it's crucial to examine the feelings of caregivers as well. It is important to analyze how family members and friends cope with a cancer diagnosis of a loved one because this drastically changes their life too. There have been several studies that have found that by taking on the role of a caregiver, there are higher rates of depression and anxiety. It is also important to acknowledge the feelings and opinions of the caregivers because they endure a great deal of emotions that are often overlooked (Edwards & Clarke, 2004). This is important because a caregiver is responsible for caring for someone who may need assistance getting through the day. The patient relies on caregivers for more than just their treatment, they rely on them for support as well. For this research, the questions that can be asked are: How do caregivers rate their quality of life? Have they noticed any physical changes to their bodies during their caregiving role? Did they accept additional help from others? What emotions do they associate with their role as a caregiver?

Positionality

In my personal experience, I have witnessed and experienced the effects of a cancer diagnosis on a loved one/caregiver. My grandfather was diagnosed with liver cancer in December of 2020. This was heartbreaking and overwhelming news for our family. We weren't

quite sure how to handle the news but knew we had to stay strong for my grandpa. My grandpa was quite stubborn and it sometimes made it difficult for us to help him. My grandmother was there with him all the time and gave him her best care and love. She tried to get him to eat, let him rest as much as possible, and tried to get him to take his medications. However, my mother was the primary caregiver for my grandpa. She was in charge of making his appointments, being in contact with his medical team, listening to the next steps for treatment, and signing all the documents regarding his care. My mother is a strong woman and is a hard worker. Throughout the past 2 ½ years, I saw how being a caregiver affected her emotionally and physically. My grandpa's diagnosis affected us all but I saw how heartbroken my mother was. She had a brave face in front of my grandpa, but some days she would just cry and become depressed. She had to sit in various meetings where they would tell her that the cancer is becoming more aggressive or that it is spreading. She did her research on what the best option would be and was the one to make those decisions for my grandpa. She expressed that she felt angry because she felt like her family could have helped more and angry that this was the situation we were in. She would say she was worried about my grandpa passing before something important like my graduation or before he could go visit his country El Salvador again. Additionally, I noticed that she would complain more about her back and body hurting. Oftentimes, they would have to rearrange or remove the furniture in my grandparents' apartment to better accommodate my grandpa. However, my mom tried to help move things around or pick up my grandpa but it ended up affecting her physically. She also carried groceries and other household items around on public transportation to give to my grandpa which made her back or shoulder hurt for a few days. I realized how being a caregiver is very emotional and can sometimes be physically demanding.

My family, especially my mom did the best we could to support my grandpa throughout his treatment. He fought hard and although he had many bad days, he made the most of his good days. Unfortunately, my grandpa passed away in February of this year. His cancer spread, his organs began to shut down, and he was tired. He passed away at his home in San Francisco and had his family around him. The past couple of months have been difficult as we are all coping differently. I have seen how much being a caregiver has affected my mother. In my grandpa's final moments, she was there with him and did her best to honor his last wishes as painful as it was for her. I know that ultimately she wanted him to be as comfortable as possible. I believe that our story provides a deeper understanding of how a cancer diagnosis affects the family and especially the family members who take on the responsibility of being a caregiver.

Background

Cancer diagnoses have been increasing within the United States in recent years. The increase in cancer diagnoses has also raised some attention to the caregivers of patients. According to a study conducted by Taylor, Fradgley, et. al, caring for a person who has been diagnosed with cancer is often associated with higher levels of distress that could affect the caregivers' health and patient outcomes (Taylor, Fradgley, et al., 2021). However, the challenges and experiences faced by caregivers are often under-researched. There have been several studies and methods proposed to help caregivers feel supported and recognized throughout their experience, however, there are still changes to be made. A cancer diagnosis has been shown to cause negative emotions in caregivers and has an impact on their physical and mental health.

When specific groups feel ignored, they are likely to experience more obstacles which make it harder for caregivers to cope with their emotions. Addressing this problem will have

benefits for caregivers and would help others understand the emotions associated with caregiving for a cancer patient.

Cancer is a disease that affects many people, emotionally and physically. There has been an increase in cancer diagnoses in recent years, and there has been more concern about how patients are being taken care of. Once an individual has been diagnosed with cancer, they tend to rely on their loved ones to help throughout their treatment and to provide support. Many family members or close friends of the individual become the patient's caregiver (Trembl, Schmidt, et al., 2021). A caregiver is responsible for administering medications, staying up to date with appointments, and providing emotional support. However, with time many researchers have discovered that caregivers can also experience difficulty in emotional and physical aspects. Recently, more studies have shown that caregivers suffer a lot throughout the process and are overwhelmed with various emotions. Additionally, caregivers' feelings and emotional and physical aspects should also be examined.

Methods

The various emotions experienced by a caregiver and the adjustments they must make to properly care for the patient is an important concept to understand. This research went in-depth about the impact a cancer diagnosis has on caregivers in a psychological and physical aspect. This research further examines how a caregiver's life changes throughout taking care of an individual with cancer and to better understand the emotions that are associated with cancer and caregiving and to provide ways in which caregivers can seek additional help.

Several objectives were defined:

1. Conduct surveys and interviews to gain more information about people's experiences with caregiving and how it has affected their daily lives

2. Determine the relationship between physical and psychological changes throughout the caregiving process
3. Examine the emotions associated with being a caregiver

These objectives are designed to provide more information on how caregivers see the situation. These objectives will give insight into the important variables that coincide with a cancer diagnosis. These objectives will help us break down a cancer diagnosis in a deeper way, examining the psychological and physical effects. The objectives also serve as a way to emphasize how emotional a cancer diagnosis is, in hopes of spreading awareness of the difficult obstacles faced by the caregivers. The long-term effects of these objectives would be concerning a solution and what it is that can be provided to caregivers so that they can better cope and prepare for this role. Some other long-term effects would be the influence different stages of cancer have on people, this would give researchers more insight into how different stages involved different or more intense emotions.

I conducted surveys to 3 participants, all over the age of 18. These participants needed to have been a caregiver for someone who has been diagnosed with cancer. This research went in-depth about the impact a cancer diagnosis has on caregivers in a psychological and physical aspect. This is to better understand the emotions that are associated with cancer and caregiving and provide ways in which caregivers can seek additional help. To better understand how caregivers are affected in a physical and psychological aspect, I used a qualitative and quantitative approach. To receive information about the experiences caregivers have had, I issued a Qualtrics survey asking participants about their caregiving experience, their daily activities, and how they rate their physical and mental health. Additionally, I conducted a semi-structured interview that went more in-depth about their experience as a caregiver for cancer patients. A

thematic analysis was also conducted to pick up common themes discussed within the interviews. These interview questions are listed.

1. Have you ever been asked about your well-being throughout your caregiving experience?
2. Can you tell me about how caregiving has impacted your life?
 - a. Is there anything that you have learned through this time?
3. What significant changes have you noticed in your body throughout this time?
 - a. Have these changes impacted your mental health? If so, in what ways?
4. How have your mood and daily activities changed? If so, how?
5. How has your physical health changed during this time? If so, how?
6. What kind of stressors have you experienced? What is the most stressful thing about caregiving?
7. Please describe your daily routine while caring for your loved one.
8. Did your role as a caregiver cause any conflicts in your relationship with others?
 - a. If yes, please describe the nature of those conflicts
 - b. If not, why do you think that is?
9. How did your levels of physical activity change throughout your caregiving role?
 - a. What were your physical activities like before you took on the role of a caregiver?
10. In your role as a caregiver, what would you describe as the most challenging activities/things?
11. How much additional help did you accept from family and friends?
 - a. If you did accept help, how did they help out? How did their help make you feel?
 - b. If you did not accept help, why not?

12. Anything else about your caregiving experience that I missed that you would like to discuss?

The information derived from the interviews was transcribed and reviewed by all participants. The data from the surveys provided a better understanding of how caregivers perceive their responsibilities. These sets of questions are designed to help us better understand the experiences and needs of caregivers. This is important because we can use this information to advocate for more resources for caregivers and to allow caregivers to speak about their experiences.

Results

The primary purpose of this study and these objectives was to further analyze the effects, both positive and negative, that are associated with caregiving. The results of this study paint the bigger picture that many people are affected by a cancer diagnosis and it is unfair to only examine one individual or one aspect of the whole. The results of this study tell the audience how important it is to understand everyone's involvement and emotions. The results also bring more attention to the fact that many people need additional help but do not reach out for the help that they need. This changes the perspective many people have on therapy/treatments and bring awareness to different ways to help people through such a traumatic time. The results showed that many caregivers find this responsibility to be an emotional journey. The participants had some common themes that came up within the surveys and interviews. Some of those common themes were feelings of depression, fear, and anger. They expressed the psychological impact caregiving had on them. They also expressed not always accepting or receiving additional support which made it harder for them. They also expressed that caregiving responsibilities sometimes mean more physically demanding tasks. Additionally, the caregivers shared how they

had less time for social life and often hid their emotions from the patient and other family members.

Discussion

The data received from the interviews and surveys provided a deeper understanding of the emotions and physical labor associated with caregiving. I found that many caregivers had similar experiences regarding the emotions they felt during their caregiving journey. They oftentimes felt overwhelmed and stressed by the situation and had to cope with their own emotions while remaining strong for their loved ones. They also reported feeling lost and worried about what to do and what could potentially be next for their loved one. The caregivers expressed various emotions with caregiving such as depression and frustration. I think that these were common emotions associated with caregiving because many of them weren't sure how to handle being a caregiver while being sad over their loved one suffering. Many people become caregivers based on feeling responsible for caring for a family member but oftentimes they do not have the resources to properly cope with their emotions. I believe that many caregivers feel the same way as the caregivers who participated in this project. I think that they do their best to provide the best care, except they struggle with their emotions. Many caregivers feel that their needs and emotions aren't important enough and often feel ignored by other people. Some people expect spouses, children, etc. to be caregivers for their family but do not realize how much of a psychological and physical impact caregiving can have on an individual.

Overall, the findings of this project agree with most of the literature in the sense that caregiving is associated with various emotions and does affect family dynamics. There were various strengths and limitations in this project. For example, a strength would be that the focus was on caregivers and further understanding their emotions associated with this responsibility.

Another strength would be investigating the physical impact caregiving has on an individual.

Regarding limitations, this project was narrowed down to just cancer caregivers. To gather more information on caregivers, the project could have focused on various illnesses and caregivers.

Another limitation would be that the sample size was small, having a bigger sample size could provide more information.

This project wanted to further understand caregivers in hopes to provide and create resources for them. The data from this project found that many caregivers feel unheard or are unaware of their resources. The results from this project can be applied in various aspects. This can help medical professionals approach caregivers differently and maybe help them throughout their journey. This project is important because it allows others to learn more about how caregiving has a physical and psychological impact on an individual. This project is also important because it helps raise awareness of caregivers' needs and makes them feel validated and heard.

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